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The practice of evidence based medicine

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Evidence-based medicine (EBM) has been defined as ‘the integration of clinical information obtained from a patient, with the best evidence available from clinical research and experience and the application of this knowledge to the prevention, diagnosis or management of disease [1, 2].

In fact EBM was defined for the first time by David Sackett as “the conscientious, explicit and judicious use of current best evidence in making decisions about the care of the individual patient”. Therefore basis of evidence based care involves the integration of the best research evidence with clinical expertise and patient values. EBM has roots going back to nineteenth century.

A major factor for the recently broadened interest has been the information explosion that increased dramatically in the last decade. Every few years the literature doubles in size, now there are more than 100,000 scientific and medical journals. Dr. Sydney Burwell 1956 (Dean, Harvard Medical School.) said "Half of what you are taught as medical students will in 10

years have been shown to be wrong. And the trouble is none of your teachers know which half.” So although the concept of practicing medicine based on sound evidence is not new, it has become more formalized with additional recent refinements that have enabled physicians to approach medical problems and evaluate medical literature with greater consistency and to deal with massive amounts of medical information via a qualitative approach.

EBM has originally been developed to aid the busy clinicians to provide the best health-care for their patients. It requires new skills of the physician, including efficient literature searching, and the application of rules of evidence in evaluating the literature. Traditionally there are four basic steps described in this approach. The first is to frame a clinically relevant question and to focus it in a way which can be answered. This is not as trivial a step as it may at first appear. The key elements of a well framed question include a description of: the patient or population; the intervention or exposure; the comparison

intervention or exposure (if relevant); and the clinical outcome(s) of interest. Such an approach can be applied whether the issue is one of diagnosis, prognosis or therapy. Having defined the question, the second step is to undertake a comprehensive review of the best available clinical evidence. This is likely to involve searching electronic databases (e.g. Medline, EMBASE, CINAHL and *The Cochrane Library*). The development of search strategies for these databases often involves expertise of information scientists who can adjust the search strategy to maximize finding all relevant studies (which increases sensitivity), but at the expense of identifying many irrelevant articles (decrease specificity). Having retrieved all potentially relevant articles which address the question, the third step is to critically appraise them. Tools have been developed to appraise studies evaluating diagnostic tests, prognostic markers, treatments, adverse effects and systematic overviews. There are many different study designs which may address this type of question. A hierarchy of such study designs has been developed with the most rigorous at the top and the least rigorous at the bottom.

The primary research study, which is considered to be the gold standard in assessing treatments, is the randomized controlled trial. The key element in this design is that the allocation of patients to the treatment group or to the comparison group is done randomly, and thus the observed differences between the treatment and the comparison group(s) will be due to the experimental treatment alone rather than to biases which may be introduced by patient characteristics, physician preferences, etc. However, even given this robust study design, the

methodological quality of randomized controlled trials may be subject to biases in other ways and these can be evaluated appropriately by checklists.

Evidence-based medicine proponents endorse the importance of clinical expertise, which uses narrative skills to integrate the information provided by the clinical method. In practicing evidence based medicine, clinicians integrate this information with that provided by sound clinical research. When tensions arise in this approach, it is usually because the narrative/intuitive paradigm has been discarded and decision making is predicated on the 'evidence' alone. Systematic reviews are the result of rigorous research, using methodology which is designed to reduce bias. As such they can provide reliable summaries of evidence. This methodology has been most comprehensively developed for systematic reviews of randomized controlled trials, but is being developed for other study designs. By searching databases of systematic reviews, such as those contained within the *Cochrane Library*, the clinician can obtain high quality evidence rapidly and reliably and enhance his/her clinical practice. The fourth step, which is to apply the evidence in clinical practice, is the point at which clinical expertise and patient values are integrated with the best available external evidence. To do this, the clinician needs to ask two questions concerning the evidence that s/he has appraised. The first is 'is this evidence sufficiently robust for me to be confident in its application?' and the second is 'is this study applicable to the patient (or population) about whose care I am deciding?'

Practitioners of evidence-based medicine have long argued that it should not be conducted from ivory towers, by individuals who have little patient contact. If it is to be applicable it needs to be practiced by all clinicians, not least because the questions or question posed need

to be relevant to routine practice. However, as will be apparent from the brief description above, the second and third steps of this approach can be very laborious. One of the most attractive and reliable of these tools is the development systematic reviews. As will be seen from the systematic review is now regarded by many as the most rigorous study design for providing information about treatments. The term systematic or scientific review is used to distinguish them from more traditional or narrative type reviews of topic areas conducted by experts in the field.

Most manuals written for evidence based practitioners do not consider textbooks to be a valuable source of information. In the relevant section in their textbook *Evidence-based Medicine* state 'we begin with textbooks only to dismiss them' later stating 'while we may find some useful information in text books about the path physiology of clinical problems it is best not use them for establishing the cause, diagnosis, prognosis, prevention or treatment of a disorder'. Part of the problem is that the material published in textbooks is written some time (often some years) before the book is published. Thus textbooks rapidly become out of date. Publishers have realized this and are trying to address this with strategies such as providing regular electronic updates more frequently than the published paper editions.

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